

LEARNING STYLES AND PREFERENCES (VISUAL, AUDITORY, KINESTETIC AND TACTICLE)

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Annotation: This article is about the learning styles such as visual auditory, kinesthetic and tactile. Furthermore, this article gives information about how to identify this styles.

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Nowadays English is becoming very important language and our government focusing on teaching English very much. On May 6, under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a video selector meeting was held regarding measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages.

At the meeting, problems in the system were thoroughly analyzed and priority tasks were determined.

- The time has come to establish a new system for teaching foreign languages in our country, which will be a solid foundation for the future. Since we have set ourselves the goal of building a competitive country, from now on school, lyceum, college and university graduates must know at least 2 foreign languages perfectly. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the activity of the head of every educational institution, - said Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

For this purpose, it was announced that the Agency for Popularization of Foreign Language Learning will be established under the Cabinet of Ministers. The head of our state emphasized the need to create suitable conditions for teachers and motivate them according to their qualifications.

Perhaps the most simple way of describing ‘learning styles’ is to say that they are different methods of learning or understanding new information, the way a person takes in, understand, expresses and remembers information.

There are 4 predominant learning styles:

1. Visual,
2. Auditory,
3. Read/Write,
4. Kinaesthetic.

While most of us may have some general idea about how we learn best, often it comes as a surprise when we discover what our predominant learning style is. Lets take a few moments and explore each of these learning styles in more detail.

Visual learners learn through seeing, so tools like diagrams, flowcharts, pictures and symbols can be key to understanding new concepts. As University style lectures tend to neglect visual components, it may be difficult for you visual learners out there to stay focused during a long lecture. When taking notes during the lessons, something to try is developing a system of symbols to replace the written word. For instance, instead of writing out “female” each time in your notes, simply use the standard symbol. Or instead of writing that the results of a particular test were positive, insert a smiley face!

For visual learners, it is often far easier for recall to work with images as oppose to working with words, as you will picture the image in your head while recalling it—far more difficult when trying to recall the word itself!

Other tricks to try for visual learners include spatially rearranging your page—instead of writing across a page horizontally, write in a way that is more descriptive of the relationship being described—for example, write the words out in a circular pattern if that more truly represents the relationship you are describing. Also, it can be useful to colour code your notes, to create more visual stimulation.

Tactile learners learn through—what else?—reading and writing. As such, university style courses suit these types of learners fairly well—plenty of text books and study notes to read. If you’re a read/write learner, pay special attention to text

book glossaries—better yet, make your own as you progress through a course. After lecture, return to your notes for review, read them over, and then create a new, condensed set of study notes. Lists can also be a very useful tool.

And a good tip for all students is to rewrite explanation and notes out into your own words. If you can't rewrite a definition or describe a concept in your own words, concisely, there is a good chance that there is an aspect of that concept that you don't fully understand. Return to this concept for further review.

Kinaesthetic Learners they learn through doing. This is perhaps the most challenging learning style for university students, as there are not always many opportunities to engage in hands on learning in lectures. For this reason, labs and tutorials become even more essential for these learners. While studying, try to incorporate all of your senses into the experience—the more of this you can do, the higher your recall will be, as you'll have multiple cues.

One way to create more useful study notes if you're a kinaesthetic learner is to fill your notes with several examples for each concept. Try taking an example from the text, or lecture, or lab, and then try creating your own example. As a general rule, the more personal your created example is, the better your recall will be for that example—and hopefully for the concept it is describing! Also try to make as much use of practise questions and exams as possible.

As was mentioned earlier, although most of us will have a sense of our learning style, we may be surprised to find out what our style really is. So if it can be challenging to determine, how do you know?

There are a lot of websites that can help ti identify the learning style of students. One of them “Online test” The “Online test” is a 16 question survey that was designed to help you self-identify your learning style by presenting you with a variety of learning or explaining scenarios and asking you how you would best make a decision, or give advice, or integrate this new information.

In the example above, response

- a) would be indicative of an auditory learner, response
- b) of a read/write learner, and response

c) of a visual learner.

To take the “Online test”, students should visit their website and take the test online.

List of references:

1. Jonassen D.H. Constructing learning environments on the web: Engaging students in meaningful learning. Ed.Tech 99: Educational Technology Conference and Exhibition 1999: Thinking Schools, Learning Nation. - 1999 - p. 45-46
2. David Nunan. Communicative Language Teaching - 2204
3. Shaw Corsini, Blake & Mouton, 1980; Horner & McGinley, 1998
4. Brown H.D. (2001). Teaching by principles: An attractive approach to language pedagogy. New York: Longman
5. Scott W.A., & Ytreberg, L.H. (2000). Teaching English to children. New York: Longman
6. Rodrieguez R.J. & White, R.N. (2003) From role play to the real world. Rowley, MA: Newbury House Publishers, Inc.
7. Horner & McGinley, 2000 Berer, Marge and Frank, Christine and Rinvoluceri, Mario. Challenge to think. Oxford University Press, 2002